

Cyclic voltammetric behaviour of isatin on HMDE in different conditions

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Manuscript received 26 December 2006, revised 30 March 2007, accepted 25 April 2007

Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of isatin on the Hanging Mercury Drop Electrode (HMDE) in aqueous KNO_3 , $1\text{N H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and acetate buffer of varying pH was investigated using Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) technique. Influence of pH, scan rate and concentration of isatin was studied on the voltammetric response in different supporting electrolyte at HMDE. In neutral medium, reduction of isatin takes place at the $\beta\text{-C=O}$ group in two steps with the consumption of one electron in each step. Between the two well defined reduction peaks, the first electron transfer, leading to radical formation, is reversible whereas second one leading to dioxindole is irreversible. The electroreduction of isatin in strong acidic medium is characterized with two irreversible reduction waves due to direct formation of dioxindole and consequently oxindole with the consumption of two and four electrons respectively, whereas in acetate buffer, of pH between 3 to 5, mainly one irreversible one electron reduction peak due to formation of dimer product, isatide is observed. Number of electrons transferred was calculated by controlled potential electrolysis. Influence of scan rate and concentration of depolariser was studied on the voltammetric response.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, isatin, electroreduction, Hanging Mercury Drop Electrode.

Indole 2,3-dione (isatin) (Fig. 1) is a synthetically versatile substrate used for the synthesis of large variety of heterocyclic compounds and serves as a raw material for drug synthesis¹⁻⁵. Its reduced species like oxindole has also been identified in urine of schizophrenic patients and suspected drug abusers^{6,7} but the synthetic and metabolic pathways of these compound and electrophysiology of isatin in biological systems is yet to be established. Isatin concentration in urine may become diagnostic marker for the clinical severity of Parkinson's disease in humans⁵.

Fig. 1. Indole 2,3-dione (isatin).

Electrochemical studies of bioactive heterocycles using various electrode systems attain prominence in recent years because of their application in electroanalysis^{8,9}. Isatin and some of its derivatives have been studied by d.c. polarography in the past^{10,11}. Determination of isatin in biological fluids and tissues has been recently done using modified solid electrodes¹². The effects of isatin in Parkinsonian rats were monitored using cyclic

voltammetry¹³. One communication on cyclic voltammetric study of isatin in aqueous KNO_3 on HMDE is reported to give only one irreversible wave¹⁴.

To obtain information about reactivity and other properties of organic compounds from voltammetric investigations, it would not be feasible to compare their reactivity in homogeneous systems to electrochemical data obtained under totally anhydrous conditions. Further practical problems of buffering and high resistance are also associated with aprotic solvents.

Encouraged by these observation, in the present work, cyclic voltammetric studies of isatin on Hanging Mercury Drop Electrode (HMDE) in aqueous 0.3 M KNO_3 , $1\text{ N H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and acetate buffer medium of varying pH have been done to shed some light on some important aspect of the mechanism of the chemical reaction at this electrode which accompany charge transfer processes.

Experimental

A software driven EG&G Potentiostat/Galvanostat Model 263A Electrochemical Chemical Analyzer (Princeton Applied Research) was employed for all the electrochemical studies. Isatin was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. 10^{-2} M Solution of isatin was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amount in appropriate vol-

ume of double distilled water in 30% ethanol. More dilute solutions were prepared by accurate dilution. The working electrode was PAR SMDE model 303A, mode one drop per scan, the counter electrode was a platinum wire and reference electrode Ag/AgCl in saturated KCl. Concentration range of isatin used in voltammetric studies was varied from 1×10^{-3} to 4×10^{-4} M. Cyclic voltammograms of the depolariser were taken in 1 N H_2SO_4 , 0.3 N KNO_3 and acetate buffer of pH range 3 to 5 to study the effect of acidity on reduction mechanism. Purging and blanketing of nitrogen were done for analyte solution placed in the electrochemical cell of 15 ml capacity for 15 min. Great care was taken in the electrode pretreatment. Mechanical polishing was done over a velvet micro cloth with an alumina suspension. A Systronics model 106 spectrophotometer is used to record UV-Visible spectra. Controlled Potential Electrolysis (CPE) was carried out for calculating number of electrons involved in the reduction process. As the products of CPE were known to differ, electrolysis was done in 2.0×10^{-3} M solution at d.m.e. in a micro cell¹⁵ keeping a blanket of nitrogen over the surface of the solution. The products were analyzed by comparison of properties with the expected product and by UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammograms of isatin on HMDE in all the selected supporting electrolytes at different sweep rate ranging from 25 to 350 mV/s were recorded for all selected concentration of isatin. The background current was recorded for such sweep rates and subtracted properly in calculating the peak currents. The peak potential (E_p , mV) and peak current (I_p , μA) were measured. The peak current in 0.3 N KNO_3 at HMDE increases smoothly up to isatin concentration of 3×10^{-3} M. The observed linear dynamic plots illustrate the feasibility of electrochemically characterizing the isatin at this electrode at low concentrations. However at higher concentrations, greater than 3 mM of the depolariser, adsorption processes is encountered as indicated from deviation from linearity of the plot between peak current and concentration of the depolariser.

Cyclic voltammetric behaviour in 1 N H_2SO_4 : In strongly acidic medium, two irreversible reduction peaks at potential around -0.22 volts and -0.38 volts are observed at all selected scan rates from 25 mV/s to 250 mV/s. Values of peak width of first cathodic peak at this pH indicates fast irreversible diffusion controlled, direct two-electron transfer process for reduction of β -C=O

group of isatin is similar to that found for other ketones¹⁶⁻¹⁸ in this medium. The α -carbonyl group is rendered electroinactive at least before hydrogen evolution through mesomeric shift with the neighbouring imino group¹⁷. The first two-electron reduction wave can be attributed to the formation of dioxindole^{11,18,19} (B, Scheme 1). However another peak seen at more negative potential, near about -0.38 volts also corresponding to two electrons may be due to reduction of dioxindole to oxindole¹¹ (D, Scheme 1).

Cyclic voltammetric behaviour in acetate buffer : Fig. 2 shows the CV response of reduction of 3 mM of isatin in acetate buffer in the pH range between 3 to 5 at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹ at 298 K. Qualitative consideration of the theory for cyclic voltammetry suggests that the system of isatin in aqueous ethanolic medium, with acetate buffer as supporting electrolyte, is characterized with mainly one significant irreversible reduction peak for chosen scan rates from 50 mV/s to 250 mV/s. Other peaks are not well defined may be due to adsorption of first electron transfer pinacol product at the electrode. As see from Fig. 2, $E_{p/2}$ values are pH dependent and shifts towards more negative potential with increasing pH indicates the occurrence of a proton transfer preceding the potential determining electron transfer step²⁰. The slope

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 3 mM isatin in acetate buffer of varying pH (from 3 to 5) scan rate 100 mV/s

Scheme 1

of $E_{1/2} - pH$ amounts to be 0.058 volts indicating one proton is involved in the rate determining step per electron transfer process. Within limits of experimental uncertainty, $E_{p/2} - E_p$ is fairly constant nearly 56–65 mV for a sweep rate ranging from 25 to 250 mV s⁻¹ indicating one electron transfer in this pH range suggesting formation of isatin dimer, isatide as main product (C, Scheme 1).

A study of effect of scan rate was made in order to evaluate the mechanism and the feasibility of electrochemical reactions involved at mercury electrode in this medium. Good linear plots of the I_p vs \sqrt{v} were obtained for all concentration of isatin shows that the reaction of isatin in this medium is diffusion controlled within the scan range employed. The shift of peak potential towards negative side with the increase of concentration of depolariser in this pH range has been assigned to irreversible reduction of depolariser.

Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out at pH 4.5 in acetate buffer at the limiting current of the

reduction wave to determine the number of electron transferred. Log I vs t plot was found linear with slope corresponding to one electron transfer. The progress of the electrolysis was monitored by TLC and by recording UV-Vis spectra at different intervals of time. With the progress of the electrolysis, absorbance at 387 nm systematically decreases and finally disappears. These observations show that no intermediate with sufficient half-life is generated during electroreduction of the compound.

Cyclic voltammetric behaviour in aqueous KNO₃ : Cyclic voltammetry study of aqueous ethanolic solution of depolariser in neutral medium on Hanging Mercury Drop Electrode at different sweep rate ranging from 50 to 250 mV/s was done for all selected concentration of isatin. Cyclic voltammetric data for different concentration of isatin in this medium is given in Table 1. Two separate well defined one electron reduction peaks around -0.6 and -0.9 volts respectively are observed in all the cases. Cyclic voltammogram of 3 mM isatin solution in 0.3 M KNO₃ at different scan rate ranging from 50 to

Fig. 3. CV responses of 3 mM isatin solution in 0.3 M KNO₃ at HMDE at different scan rates from 50 to 250 mV/s.

250 mV is shown in Fig. 3. Peak separation ($E_{pa} - E_{pc}$) for first one electron reduction wave suggests that first electron transfer is almost reversible as corresponding anodic peak is observed at all scan rates. The radical anion formed in the first step is not protonated to any considerable degree before being dimerised or reduced and the uncharged isatin predominating in this medium (Scheme 1). There is, however, a certain influence of the depolariser concentration on peak potential suggesting that dimerization is also involved in the process. A good second peak due to reduction of radical anion to dioxindole is observed on HMDE at all select scan rates in this medium. $E_{p/2} - E_p$ values show one electron transfer for both the reduction waves. Second reduction peak broadens and shift towards negative potential with increase in scan rate as can be seen from Fig. 3. This suggests that the reaction may be influenced by adsorption processes. The fact that $E_{p/2}$ values shifted towards negative potential with increasing depolariser concentration indicates irreversible diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process (Table 1).

The predominant product of the two electron reduc-

Table 1

Conc. isatin (mM)	Scan rate (mV/s)	1st peak						2nd peak		
		$-E_{pc}$ (mV)	$-I_{pc}$ (μ A)	$-E_{pc} - E_{pc/2}$ (mV)	$-E_{pa}$ (mV)	$-I_{pa}$ (μ A)	$-E_{pa} - E_{pc}$ (mV)	$-E_{pc}$ (mV)	$-I_{pc}$ (μ A)	$-E_{pc} - E_{pc/2}$ (mV)
1	50	604.7	2.01	68.7	521.8	0.04	77	883.3	2.69	57.3
	100	603.5	2.50	63.7	534.4	0.61	68	902.1	3.13	70.1
	150	603.5	2.97	66.5	537.5	1.00	66	936.8	3.48	81.8
	200	603.5	3.56	70.5	537.5	1.37	66	955.6	3.96	84.6
	250	603.5	3.93	66.5	537.5	1.58	66	971.3	4.20	87.3
2	50	622.4	3.14	71	521.8	817 nA	89	899	4.32	56
	100	622	4.11	72.2	540.7	1.28	72.8	921	5.24	67
	150	622.4	4.95	73	543.8	1.54	74.6	943	5.84	76
	200	622.4	6.0	74.4	537.5	1.81	76	993.3	6.81	80
	250	622.4	6.63	72	537.4	2.05	74	1.00 V	7.28	98.7
3	50	630.2	4.32	71.7	518.7	994 nA	84	895.9	6.29	52
	100	630.2	5.66	72	537.5	1.50	82.4	921	7.49	64
	150	631.8	6.88	72.8	537.5	1.85	82	933.6	8.23	69
	200	631.8	8.28	70.5	540.7	2.28	78	961.9	9.39	73
	250	631.8	9.36	71.8	547	2.62	78.6	1.0 V	10.21	84
4	50	631.8	5.12	74.8	528.1	1.27	88	895.9	8	46
	100	632	7.33	70.8	528.1	1.79	87	915	10.37	56
	150	631.8	7.58	70	528.1	1.87	84	930.4	9.61	56
	200	631.8	10.61	71.1	531.3	2.51	84	952.5	12.61	61
	250	631.8	11.58	69.1	534.3	2.94	83	980.8	13.18	84

tion in this medium was identified to be dioxindole by conducting controlled potential coulometry at plateau potential of the second irreversible wave. The progress of the electrolysis was monitored by TLC and by recording UV-Vis spectra at different intervals of time.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Department of Science & Technology, Delhi for financial support to the work.

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